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THE FIRST REPORT ON NOVEL EXOPOLYSACCHARIDE SYNTHESIS BY *RHIZOBIUM RADIOBACTER* AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION

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A wide group rhizobacteria are characterized with synthesis of exopolysaccharides (EPS) and these biopolymers are differed due to their physical-chemical properties: structure, monomer content, molar weight etc. (Rasulov et al., 2020). Among these rhizobacteria, *Rhizobium* genus representatives also reported for production of EPS (Rasulov et al., 2017). EPS of the genus were documented for effective formation of symbiosis, salt-stress mitigation (Rasulov et al., 2020). *Rhizobium* species and strains produced a wide variety of EPS structures, which differ each other with carbohydrates types and molar ratio (Rasulov et al., 2020). Here we report synthesis and characterization of a novel EPS by strain *Rhizobium radiobacter* 36, isolated from the nodules of soybean (*Glycine max L.*).

EPS was isolated after three days of cultivation of the strain in potato-sucrose broth (Rasulov et al., 2020). The strain's identification was performed by 16S rRNA gene sequencing (Rasulov and Pattaeva, 2024). FT-IR, GC-MS and SEM of EPS was performed as reported elsewhere (Rasulov et al., 2020). Metal removal and its assessment was done as described in our previous research (Rasulov et al., 2020).

16S rRNA gene sequencing indicated that the strain belongs to the species *Rhizobium radiobacter* (NCBI GenBank accession number PP859459.1). FT-IR analysis of the crude EPS confirmed its polysaccharide nature (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of EPS produced by *R. radiobacter* 36.

The stretching vibrations observed at 3281 cm⁻¹ correspond to hydroxyl groups (-OH), indicating extensive hydrogen bonding typical of polysaccharides (Kačuráková and Wilson, 2001), while the band at 2930 cm⁻¹ represents the C-H stretching vibrations of aliphatic groups (Hong et al., 2021). The region between 1242–1393 cm⁻¹ is associated with bending vibrations of -COH, -OCH, and -CCH groups, reflecting the complex carbohydrate backbone. The peak at 1633 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching vibrations of carbonyl groups (C=O) from uronic acid residues or the presence of

adsorbed water molecules. Additionally, the strong bands at 1022–1077 cm^{-1} signify the C-O-C glycosidic bond, which is a key structural feature of polysaccharide chains (Kanamarlapudi and Muddada, 2017; Hong et al., 2021). Peaks at 916.33 and 891.45 cm^{-1} confirm the β -configuration of the glycosidic bonds in the glucose-rich succinoglycan backbone (Hong et al., 2021). GC-MS analysis revealed that the EPS comprises 88.053% glucose and 11.947% galactose, with a molar ratio of 7.36:1, indicating that it is a succinoglycan-type EPS. Until now no EPS was reported with a such monomer molar ratio. Based on the results it can be proposed the following structure:

The SEM image of EPS (Fig.2) shows a fibrous, porous, and sponge-like matrix with aggregated polymeric strands, indicating strong water retention and ion-binding capacity. Its rough, multilayered surface supports salt ion entrapment (Na^+ , Ca^{2+}), contributing to soil stabilization and plant growth under saline stress.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph of EPS sample

One of the important properties of the EPS was its enhanced capacity to remove Ca^{2+} in the presence of Na^+ ions. Sodium (Na^+) is a primary contributor to salinity, which impedes most biological processes, while calcium (Ca^{2+}) plays a crucial role in soil stabilization. In the presence of 2.0% NaCl (a source of Na^+), the EPS removed 31.95 mg/g of Ca^{2+} .

Based on the research, an EPS consisting of 88.053% glucose and 11.947% galactose was isolated and identified from the culture broth of *R. radiobacter* 36. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of a novel EPS structure produced by *R. radiobacter* 36. The EPS demonstrated enhanced activity in solubilizing insoluble calcium salts and binding the released Ca^{2+} ions.

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